

TIMBERHAUS

D5.1 – TIMBERHAUS Communities of Practice

WP5, T5.1

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Acronym	Full Term
CEM	Common Engagement Methodology
CRM	Contact Relationship Management
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental
QR	Quick Response
SDM	System Dynamics Modelling

Table 1. Acronyms

1. Executive Summary

D5.1 covers M1-M18 of Task 5.1. Its three components, stakeholder mapping and analysis, the Common Engagement Methodology, and the establishment of Communities of Practice, are designed to work together as a set of interconnected tools. The stakeholder mapping identifies who is in the ecosystem and feeds into how the project engages with them. The Common Engagement Methodology sets the principles that govern that engagement across all three partner cities. The Communities of Practice are where both are applied, bringing mapped actors into structured dialogue and generating the local insight that in turn deepens the stakeholder map. Information flows in both directions and it is this circularity that gives T5.1 its role as a project-wide coordination instrument, providing the methodological foundations on which co-creation, modelling and policy engagement across WP5, WP6 and WP7 are built.

For the stakeholder mapping and analysis, a shared Excel-based system was developed with partners from WP5, WP6 and WP7 and issued as live files on the project SharePoint, one per city and one at EU level, designed as a working tool capable of filtering and cross-referencing stakeholders by sector, geography and project task. Across 121 categorised entries spanning the four sheets, the dataset is strong in public sector and decision-making actors, processing and manufacturing, and research and academia, reflecting both the governance-heavy nature of the wood construction challenge and the networks through which mapping has so far been built. Circular economy actors, financial institutions and construction operators are identified as priorities as engagement deepens. What the dataset does not yet fully capture is not a gap in engagement so much as a gap in recording, and addressing this systematically ahead of the second round of summits will widen the actor base available to subsequent tasks.

The Common Engagement Methodology (CEM) governs how TIMBERHAUS engages with its partner cities and their stakeholders across work packages and over the project lifetime, integrating central coordination, place-based Communities of Practice and cross-sector dialogue. In practice it required genuine adaptation to local context from the outset. Rather than engaging all three cities jointly, the consortium moved quickly to city-specific approaches, given the divergence in language, ambition and prior experience with timber construction. The CEM is a live reference framework and will continue to evolve in response to what the second and third rounds of engagement reveal.

When it came to the Communities of Practice, rather than establishing formal communities with fixed governance, the consortium concluded that the Stakeholder Summits would function as the primary vehicle for community building, supplemented by targeted online engagement between them. The first round has now been completed across all three cities. Each summit surfaced a distinct local picture: Baia Mare identified illegal logging, high construction costs and workforce gaps as its core challenges; Siena, where timber construction is relatively new, focused on building foundational interest and identified cultural preference for conventional materials as a significant barrier alongside genuine opportunity in the region's artisanal heritage; Berlin engaged a more experienced sector and used thematic workshop groups to move beyond baseline challenges into specific priorities around regulation, funding, education and procurement. Across all three,

interactive formats consistently outperformed presentational ones and outreach to forest managers and construction sector actors is identified as a gap to address in the second round.

With T5.1 formally concluding at M18, the work it has established is carried forward across multiple tasks in WP5, WP6 and WP7. The stakeholder actor base passes to T6.2 for System Dynamics Modelling of the wood construction value chain. The CEM continues as the guiding framework for city engagement across T6.1, T6.3 and T6.4, which take forward respectively the New European Bauhaus approach, co-design activities and strategy games with local stakeholders. The Communities of Practice are sustained through the second and third rounds of Stakeholder Summits, with the second round expected in Baia Mare and Siena between October and November 2026 and in Berlin in early 2027. The three components of T5.1 therefore do not conclude so much as disperse into other delivery work within the project.

2. Introduction and Scope

2.1. Project Context

TIMBERHAUS is a four-year Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action bringing together 20 organisations from across Europe to accelerate the climate-smart use of wood in construction. The project is grounded in a straightforward but urgent observation: the construction sector accounts for roughly 40 per cent of EU CO₂ emissions and half of all materials extracted, yet wood, one of the few genuinely carbon-storing building materials, remains significantly underused. TIMBERHAUS sets out to change that.

It does so across three interconnected strands: developing new wood processing technologies that draw on machine learning to make better use of underutilised and post-consumer timber; co-creating circular wood building blueprints with three European partner cities, grounded in local context and culture; and building the policy, market and knowledge infrastructure needed to scale these solutions across Europe. The work is tested and embedded in the real conditions of Berlin, Baia Mare and Siena, three cities chosen for the diversity of their starting points, ambitions and wood construction landscapes.

2.2. Scope of This Deliverable

WP5 provides the systemic and contextual analysis that underpins the co-creation and scaling activities of TIMBERHAUS, assessing the technical, regulatory, economic, social and knowledge dimensions of the transition to climate-smart wood construction across the three partner cities and at European level.

D5.1 reports on the work completed under Task 5.1. The goal of Task 5.1 was to set up Communities of Practice for climate-smart use of wood in construction. To achieve this goal, the task involved developing and implementing three interconnected components, each of which is addressed in a dedicated section of this report.

The first component is stakeholder mapping and analysis (Section 3). This covers the process by which the forest-to-city stakeholder ecosystem has been identified, categorised and recorded across the three partner cities and at EU level. It describes the collaborative methods used, the analytical framework applied, the findings emerging from the current dataset, and the lessons learnt from implementation to date.

The second component is the Common Engagement Methodology (Section 4). This sets out the principles and practical approach that govern how TIMBERHAUS engages with partner cities and their local stakeholders across work packages and over the lifetime of the project. It covers the design rationale, the operationalisation of the methodology in each city, and the adaptations made in response to local context and emerging experience.

The third component is the Communities of Practice (Section 5). This describes the approach taken to establish or strengthen multi-actor Communities of Practice in each partner city,

connecting local stakeholder networks to the wider TIMBERHAUS consortium and to existing platforms including the Build-in-Wood Community. It reports on the first round of Stakeholder Summits held in Baia Mare, Siena and Berlin, and sets out the next steps for sustained community engagement.

The three components are closely interconnected, with information and insight flowing in both directions between them, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Relationships between the three core components of D5.1

2.3. Relationship to Other WP5 Deliverables and Wider Project Tasks

D5.1 is the first of four outputs from WP5 and the earliest to be submitted. The four WP5 tasks run in parallel rather than in sequence, each addressing a distinct dimension of the systemic context for wood construction: T5.1 on stakeholder mapping and Communities of Practice; T5.2 on challenges and opportunities analysis; T5.3 on the policy and regulatory landscape; and T5.4 on EU best practice.

The deliverable also connects directly to WP6 Task 6.2, which is developing System Dynamics Models of the wood construction value chain. That task draws on structured stakeholder input to model local governance, resource flows and systemic relationships. A well-populated and analytically categorised stakeholder record is therefore of direct value to Task 6.2 as the project progresses.

At a broader project level, T5.1 was specifically designed to establish a common framework and methodology for multi-stakeholder engagement to be used across the project as a whole and above all with WP6, where the research carried out in WP5 is tested directly with the cities. In this sense, the Common Engagement Methodology described in Section 4 of this report is not solely a WP5 instrument. It is a project-wide coordination tool designed to ensure that engagement across WP5, WP6 and WP7 is coherent, avoids duplication, and draws on a shared understanding of stakeholder relationships and local context.

2.4. Ongoing Iteration

This deliverable covers M1 to M18, but stakeholder mapping, community building and the deployment of an engagement methodology are inherently iterative. What is described here represents the state of work at the point of submission, not a finished product. The most important outputs of T5.1 are working systems rather than static documents, and they will continue to develop as the project moves further into the co-creation and scaling phases. The deeper relational analysis of how stakeholders connect and where leverage points lie is taken forward in Tasks 6.2 and 6.3, which build on the actor-level foundation established here.

3. Stakeholder Mapping and Analysis

3.1. Introduction

Stakeholder mapping is a key task for the whole of TIMBERHAUS, as it illuminates which organisations are working in the forest-to-city value chain of the three partner cities and relevant parties at EU level and thus how they can be brought together to advance the aims of the overall project. Specifically, the task centred on identifying, analysing and mapping the forest-to-city stakeholder ecosystem.

This section goes through the processes undertaken to develop a workable method for gathering and recording stakeholder information. Starting with the theoretical framework that was proposed, followed by testing through implementation with partner cities and a lightweight analysis of the stakeholder ecosystem.

This stakeholder mapping remains an ongoing exercise since the identification of stakeholders will continue throughout the project. Thus, the most important output of this task is a system for storing and analysing stakeholders going forward.

In addition, the deeper analytical work focused on full stakeholder analysis, governance-model mapping, and interaction and resource-flow mapping is carried out by Task 5.2 (PESTLE analysis), Task 6.2 (System Dynamics Modelling) and Task 6.3 (co-design engagement). It is for this reason that the task leaders within WP5 and WP6 coordinated closely throughout this process.

3.2. Collaborative mapping session

Shortly after the first General Assembly (M1), all partners were brought together online for an initial session to begin mapping stakeholders collaboratively. Using a shared Miro board (See Figure 2), participants mapped out the organisations and individuals they considered relevant to the forest-to-city value chain in their respective cities and at EU level. The session was valuable in establishing a shared starting point and a common understanding of the landscape across the partnership before the more structured capture process began.

Figure 2. Shared Miro Board for initial stakeholder mapping

3.3. Initial Framework

Following the collaborative Miro session, the starting point for the more detailed stakeholder mapping system was; where should the stakeholder information live?

For the stakeholder mapping to make sense to everyone in the project and contain enough detailed information, we needed something that is familiar, easy to use but also capable of being a powerful analysis tool, able to cross-reference many data points. The key decision was whether to use a system mapping tool such as Miro or Kumu, or a tagged database such as Airtable or Excel.

Following internal discussion, Airtable was initially selected as the central system to test. The case for it was that it functions as a lightweight customer relationship management (CRM) system, allowing contacts, organisations, work packages, tasks, activities and interactions to be cross-linked in one place rather than held in separate files. This matters because the stakeholder database is not just a list. It needs to be a working tool that can produce for example, a filtered list of all Berlin-based contacts relevant to a particular workshop, or all organisations tagged to WP6, without anyone having to manually sort through a spreadsheet each time. Airtable was designed to do that work automatically once the data was in place. The long-term vision expressed at the time was for it to serve as the central database for the TIMBERHAUS consortium.

The database was structured around four areas:

1. A contacts and organisations layer as the foundation;
2. A tasks and work package owners layer to link contacts to project responsibilities;
3. An interaction tracker to log individual engagements with stakeholders over time;
4. A key activities table grouping those interactions under the broader activities they relate to, such as a stakeholder summit or a series of workshops.

Based on this agreement, the Airtable was built (See Figure 3) and preliminarily populated in early 2025.

A	Activity Name	Organisations	Key Activity
1	Stakeholder Summit 2		Stakeholder Summit
2	Stakeholder Summit 1		Stakeholder Summit
3	Stakeholder mapping Group Exercise 2		Online Workshop
4	Stakeholder mapping for Europe	Climate-KIC, UrbaSofia, ETH Zur	Desk Research
5	Blueprints	Waugh Thistleton Architects	Design work
6	Berlin Housing Materials workshop	Climate-KIC	In Person Workshop
7	Online workshops on climate-smart use of wood and challe...	UrbaSofia, Climate-KIC, ETH Zur	Online Workshop
8	System Dynamic model	ETH Zurich	Desk Research
9	Causal loop diagram	ETH Zurich	Desk Research
10	Game design	ETH Zurich	Desk Research, Design
11	Game testing	ETH Zurich	In Person Workshop
12	Game session with partner cities	ETH Zurich	Stakeholder Summit
13	NEB Workshops	Climate-KIC	Stakeholder Summit

Figure 3. Airtable as the central database for the stakeholder mapping

3.4. Testing through implementation

With the central database established, the next step was to develop a means by which stakeholder information could be gathered in a structured way and fed into it. It became clear early on that asking city representatives and partners to input directly into Airtable was not practical, as the tool was unfamiliar to many and the learning curve risked slowing the process down at a critical early stage. The response was to develop a structured Excel template that could serve as a first point of capture, with data possibly being transferred into Airtable as the records built up over time. At this stage, whether the Airtable remains the intended long-term home for all stakeholder data depends on needs emerging in the remainder of the project.

The Excel template used was developed collaboratively (See Figure 4). A Miro session brought together partners from across WP5, WP6 and WP7 to establish what information would be most useful to capture, followed by a period of review and iteration over email as partners tested the template and fed back on its structure. The result was a template designed to serve multiple goals at once, meeting the needs of stakeholder engagement, event targeting and analytical work across the work packages.

Stakeholder Sheet									Information
<p>READ ME Please use this sheet to save and categorise your stakeholders for the whole of the Timberhaus project. Doing so will help us to deliver on Timberhaus goals and ensure activities involve the correct organisations and individuals</p> <p>INSTRUCTIONS All instructions are in bold red text. Please refer to the 'Information' and 'Question Prompts' for guidance on how to categorise stakeholders. Please try and fill in ALL FIELDS. The more information, the better the result for everyone.</p>									<p>Stakeholders might fit in certain categories (to the right, e.g. architecture) but they might have cross-cutting skills which enable them to work in areas outside of their sectors. They might design buildings but also have good knowledge of policy frameworks, or they might manage forests but also understand harvesting and manufacturing. Please add as much information as possible.</p> <p>Question Prompt Add which collection of activities this stakeholder would be best suited to support. E.g., Policy/regulation work, architectural design workshops, etc.</p>
Stakeholder Number	Contact	Organisation	Primary Email	Secondary Email	Submitted by (Person, First and Last name)	Submitted by (Organisation)	Select Work Packages (WP) to pass Contact Ownership to (drop down below):	ACTIVITIES to be participated in	IMPORTANT - Please type in as much detail as possible
1	John Smith	Smith & Sons	john.smith@smithson	None	George McLoughlin	Climate-KIC	WP 5/6/7: COLLABC		
<p>Information</p> <p>The main partner cities for Timberhaus are Berlin, Baia Mare and Siena. Most stakeholders are likely to be linked to these cities. However many may come from other areas of the EU or beyond.</p> <p>Information</p> <p>There are intended to be a number of stakeholders from a range of sectors participating in Timberhaus. Thus it is important to categorise them properly. Please view the second sheet tab titled 'Categories for Reference' to help you select the most appropriate Primary and Sub-sector.</p> <p>Information</p> <p>Influence determines a stakeholder's ability to shape policies, funding, and industry decisions. Identifying key decision-makers helps prioritise engagement and navigate potential blockers or enablers.</p> <p>Information</p> <p>Interest reflects a stakeholder's engagement in the forest-to-wood value chain. Understanding their motivations ensures targeted collaboration with those most invested in Timberhaus objectives.</p> <p>Information</p> <p>Stakeholders vary in their environmental impact, from driving sustainability to contributing to deforestation. Understanding their role helps Timberhaus align with partners who support responsible forestry and wood utilisation practices.</p> <p>Information</p> <p>Stakeholders play different roles in the value chain, from core producers to supporting services. Mapping their market position ensures strategic engagement with key economic players.</p>									
<p>Question Prompt</p> <p>Which city or region is this stakeholder linked with?</p> <p>Question Prompt</p> <p>What is the primary sector that this stakeholder sits under?</p> <p>Question Prompt</p> <p>Within the primary sector, which sub-sector does this stakeholder sit under?</p> <p>Question Prompt</p> <p>What is the stakeholder's level of influence in their sector/market/policy landscape?</p> <p>To what extent can this stakeholder impact decision-making within the forest-to-wood value chain?</p> <p>Question Prompt</p> <p>What is the anticipated level of stakeholder interest in participating in Timberhaus?</p> <p>How likely is this stakeholder to take action (supportive or obstructive) regarding forestry-related initiatives?</p> <p>Question Prompt</p> <p>Considering this stakeholder's role within their sector, their level of influence, and their interest in sustainability, how would you rate their current impact on sustainable forestry practices and/or wood utilisation?</p> <p>Question Prompt</p> <p>Considering this stakeholder's position within the forest-to-wood value chain, their economic influence, and their level of activity, how would you rate their role in the market?</p>									
<p>Use drop downs below</p> <p>City or Region</p> <p>Sector</p> <p>Level of Influence</p> <p>Level of Interest</p> <p>Scale of Sustainability Impact</p> <p>Extent of Market Role</p>									
<p>Other - See Additional Notes</p> <p>Forestry and Resource Management</p> <p>Logging companies</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Somewhat Interested</p> <p>Not sustainable</p> <p>Secondary Market Position: Supporting Act</p>									

Figure 4. Excel template for the stakeholder mapping

Stakeholders are captured against a primary sector and sub-sector classification covering nine sectors intended to span the full forest-to-city value chain and quadruple helix:

- Public Sector and Decision Makers;
- Forestry and Resource Management;
- Processing, Manufacturing and Retail;
- Design and Planning;
- Construction and Installation;
- End-of-Life and Circular Economy;
- Research, Academia and Innovation;
- Civil Society and Advocacy;
- Financial Sector;

- Other.

Four analytical dimensions are recorded for each stakeholder on a five-point scale: Level of Influence, Level of Interest, Scale of Sustainability Impact and Extent of Market Role. WP and activity tags allow each entry to be pre-sorted for downstream use at the point of capture rather than retrospectively.

Four parallel versions of the template were issued as live files hosted on the TIMBERHAUS SharePoint: one each for Berlin, Baia Mare and Siena, and one at EU level. Keeping the files live rather than circulating attachments was a deliberate choice, ensuring a single authoritative version of each sheet that could be updated continuously and plugged into Airtable, avoiding multiple versions which are hard to find and risk being incorrect.

Guidance and instructions were sent to city representatives to support the process, and further touchpoints were created at in-person events, including a QR code sign-up at all three city summits to make it as easy as possible for new stakeholders to be added on the ground.

The population of the sheets has been an iterative process, as expected from the outset. Many of the stakeholders who will ultimately appear in the records are external parties who come into contact with the project through specific tasks and events over its lifetime, and the sheets will continue to grow as that engagement deepens.

3.5. Analysis

3.5.1. Overview

Across the four sheets, Berlin, Baia Mare, Siena and EU level, 121 categorised stakeholders have been recorded at the time of writing. All four sheets remain works in progress and sit alongside a broader programme of in-person engagement activity across the three cities that is discussed in detail later in this report. The figures below reflect the current state of the dataset and will grow as the project continues.

Figure 5. Chart of mapped stakeholders by city and EU level

As shown in Figure 5, the distribution varies across the four contexts. Siena is the most populated sheet, with EU level and Berlin following. Baia Mare has eight confirmed entries at this stage, for reasons discussed below.

The sector and category data gathered across the four sheets provides the empirical foundation from which governance models, interrelationships and resource flows between stakeholders can be examined. This deeper relational analysis is pursued in Tasks 5.2, 6.2 and 6.3 alongside the co-creation process. What follows is a first account of the shape of the ecosystem as it currently stands.

3.5.2. What the sectors reveal

Figure 6. Chart of primary sector distribution by city and EU level

Seven of the nine defined primary sectors have at least some representations across the four sheets. As shown in Figure 6, Public Sector and Decision Makers is the largest group overall with 34 entries, followed by Processing and Manufacturing and Retail with 21, Research, Academia and Innovation with 18, Design and Planning and Forestry and Resource Management each with 13, Construction and Installation with 12 and Civil Society and Advocacy with 10.

Two sectors have limited or no representation in the confirmed dataset at this stage: End-of-Life and Circular Economy, the Financial Sector, and a small number of stakeholders who could not yet be assigned to a defined primary sector (Other). This is not unusual at this point in a mapping process. The dataset has been built primarily through existing partner networks, which naturally reflect the sectors those partners work closest to. As the mapping continues, there is good scope to bring in circular economy actors, who will become increasingly relevant as the project engages with end-of-life material questions, and financial sector organisations, whose involvement will support the scaling ambitions of WP7.

3.5.3. Cities and EU Stakeholder Details

Interestingly, the three partner cities present quite different stakeholder landscapes in the dataset. The routes through which stakeholders were identified varied across them, reflecting local networks, working practices and the pace at which information was captured. It is important to note that the dataset represents one strand of a wider engagement effort. All three cities have run active in-person programmes alongside the mapping work, and the full picture of stakeholder engagement in each city is discussed in a later section of this report.

3.5.3.1. Siena

Figure 7. Chart showing number of stakeholders by primary sector in Siena

Siena is the most populated sheet. Its largest group is Public Sector and Decision Makers with 18 entries, nine of those being regional and local authorities. Forestry and Construction each contribute seven entries, and Design and Planning a further five. This spread across multiple parts of the value chain provides a strong basis for co-creation planning and reflects the breadth of the stakeholder network that has developed in the city.

3.5.3.2. Berlin

Figure 8. Chart showing number of stakeholders by primary sector in Berlin

Berlin's sheet is heavily concentrated in two clusters, Public Sector with 11 entries and Research, Academia and Innovation with 10. Together these account for more than two-thirds of the Berlin sheet. This reflects the city's character as a regulatory and knowledge hub. Civil Society actors and those working in construction and production are natural additions as the mapping develops and would extend the dataset's reach further along the value chain. As with the other cities, the sheet data sits alongside an active in-person engagement programme that has brought a wider range of actors into the project directly.

3.5.3.3. Baia Mare

Figure 9. Chart showing number of stakeholders by primary sector in Baia Mare

Baia Mare has eight categorised stakeholders at this stage, with five in Public Sector, two in Forestry and one in Design and Planning. The sheet data alone does not reflect the full extent of stakeholder engagement in the city. As discussed later in this report, Baia Mare has been the site of active in-person engagement activities, and a network of stakeholders has developed through that work. Capturing this more fully in the dataset as the project continues will give a more complete picture of the ecosystem that has already taken shape on the ground.

3.5.3.4. EU-level

Figure 10. Chart showing number of stakeholders by primary sector at EU level

The EU sheet differs from the city sheets, reflecting the nature of EU-level networks. Processing and Manufacturing and Retail is the largest sector with 11 entries, followed by Research, Academia and Innovation and Civil Society and Advocacy each with six. European regulatory and policy bodies are a natural area for further development as the project moves into its later phases, and adding Public Sector entries at EU level would strengthen the sheet's utility for the dissemination and policy engagement work of WP7.

The EU sheet is best understood as complementary to the city sheets. Where the city sheets are strongest in governance and local institutional actors, the EU sheet fills in industry, research and advocacy. Read together, the four sheets sketch a more complete picture of the forest-to-city ecosystem than any one of them could alone.

3.5.4. Influence, interest and engagement readiness

Where stakeholders have been categorised, the sheets also capture influence, interest, sustainability orientation and market role. The analysis draws on the data from those sheets.

Figure 11. Chart showing rated influence levels of stakeholders by city and EU level

The influence profile across the dataset is broadly positive. Twenty-three stakeholders are rated as Influential and 26 as Moderately influential, as shown in Figure 11. This reflects the tendency of established, well-networked actors to be the most readily identifiable at this stage of a mapping exercise and is consistent with the strong institutional presence noted in the sector analysis above.

Figure 12. Matrix showing influence versus interest levels of stakeholders at city and EU level

The influence-interest matrix in Figure 12 covers stakeholders from Siena, Berlin and EU level and plots both dimensions together, giving a clearer picture of the engagement landscape than either axis alone.

The upper-right quadrant is encouraging. A substantial group of Influential and Moderately Influential stakeholders also register high or moderate interest, representing actors who are both well-positioned to shape outcomes and already engaged with the work. Very few sit in the upper-left, where influence is high, but interest is low, which suggests the dataset has not over-indexed on powerful but indifferent actors.

The largest single concentration sits at Neutral influence and Moderate interest, with 14 stakeholders at that position, and a further cluster of Somewhat Influential but highly interested actors appears in the lower-right. Both groups represent real engagement potential that can deepen through community of practice activities as the project progresses.

Figure 13. Chart showing rated sustainability levels of stakeholders by city and EU level

Sustainability scores are the most consistently positive dimension across the dataset. Partners inputting into the Excel were prompted with the following question which serves as the decider for the degree of sustainability; “Considering this stakeholder’s role within their sector, their level of influence, and their interest in sustainability, how would you rate their current impact on sustainable forestry practices and/or wood utilisation?”. As such, thirty-nine stakeholders are rated as Highly sustainable and only three as Not sustainable (See Figure 13), which is broadly aligned with what one would expect from organisations engaging with a climate-focused project of this nature. Though it must be noted this is perception based in that it depends on the opinion of the individual inputting into the stakeholder sheet, so this indicator should be read with caution.

Figure 14. Chart showing rated market roles of stakeholders by city and EU level

The market role dimension was included to enrich the interpretation of influence and interest by capturing where a stakeholder sits economically within the forest-to-city value chain. Knowing whether an organisation is a dominant producer, a niche supplier, or an advisory body helps explain why its influence or interest registers at the level it does, and points to where leverage and potential bottlenecks in the system are most likely to lie. This makes it a useful input for later project work, particularly the System Dynamics Modelling in Task 6.2, which depends on understanding the economic weight and position of actors across the chain.

The five categories used, shown in Figure 14, run from Primary Market Position: Core Actor at one end to Limited Market Position: Peripheral Actor at the other. With only five stakeholders currently sitting at Core Actor level, the dataset at this stage is weighted towards enabling, advisory and facilitative roles. This is consistent with the broader profile of the dataset, which is strong in institutional and governance actors and has less representation at the production end of the value chain. As the mapping develops and more manufacturing and construction organisations are captured, the distribution across these categories is expected to shift.

3.5.5. Where things stand

Across all three cities and at EU level, the mapping provides a growing foundation for co-creation planning. The dataset continues to develop alongside a wider programme of in-person engagement activity, and together these strands give the project an increasingly detailed picture of the forest-to-city stakeholder ecosystem. Extending coverage into circular economy, financial and civil society actors across all contexts would further enrich the dataset and widen the range of organisations available to draw into the activities ahead.

The analysis here is a first reading of an ecosystem still being built. The work of understanding how these actors connect, what governance structures shape their relationships, and where the leverage points lie is taken forward in Tasks 5.2, 6.2 and 6.3, using the stakeholder data gathered here as its foundation.

3.6. Lessons learnt

The implementation of the stakeholder mapping exercise surfaced a number of useful lessons that will shape how the process is approached going forward.

The most significant finding was that the Excel template, while well-designed for its purpose, proved difficult to populate consistently without sustained support and follow-up. Engagement with the sheets varied across contributors, and in a number of cases stakeholder information was captured through other means rather than directly into the sheet. The analytical work undertaken for this report also surfaced that entries that were not categorised against the defined sector taxonomy could not be included in the cross-city analysis. Ensuring that all future entries are completed to the level required by the template, and in particular that a primary sector is assigned to every stakeholder, will significantly improve the utility of the dataset.

The initial decision to centre the framework on Airtable proved to be ahead of where the team and partners were in practice. Airtable is a powerful tool, but its unfamiliarity created a barrier at the point of capture rather than easing it. The pivot to Excel as the primary capture tool was the right response, and the sheets remain the active point of entry.

Transfer into Airtable remains a possibility once records are sufficiently built up, but should not be seen as the primary goal. The interaction tracker, which was part of the original Airtable design, became too cumbersome to maintain and will not be carried forward. Shared Word documents hosted on the TIMBERHAUS SharePoint serve the same purpose for recording notes from city calls and meetings.

Looking ahead, all sheets will continue to be updated before the end of the project. The in-person engagement activity described in more detail later in the report has already brought a wider network of stakeholders into view and engaged than can be reflected through an written dataset.

4. Common Engagement Methodology

4.1. Introduction

Establishing what in this section is referred to as a common engagement methodology, or CEM, was a key element of T5.1. As per the GA, it would be created to ensure that co-creation sessions are designed to be a space which fosters multi-actor consensus, joint value creation, and sets the stage for action and impact.

This was viewed to be particularly important thanks to the priority placed on a place-based approach in TIMBERHAUS, to ensure that any research and technical developments resonate with those who would be implementing them on the ground in a range of contexts across Europe, specifically testing in Baia Mare (Romania), Berlin (Germany), and Siena (Italy).

This local engagement within TIMBERHAUS incorporates data provision, involvement in workshops, technical and thematic co-design activities, and strategy games, to name but a few elements of the approach. Noting that these activities take place across four years, across three different partner cities, across languages, and with interconnections with multiple topics and WPs, it was crucial to establish basic principles of engagement and coordination both with the partner cities directly, with their local stakeholders, and for learning loops between the cities as well from the start.

In this way, the CEM, whilst developed and iterated under T5.1, is in many ways effectively implemented through the delivery of tasks in WP6 and consequently WP7, where the interaction with the cities themselves takes place.

This section will therefore detail both the theory behind the CEM and how it has been implemented in practice, looking at the nuances across each city's engagement strategy. It should be noted that this remains an iterative process, as is the nature of working with cities in such work and will be reviewed and adapted as the project progresses.

4.2. Principles of the Common Engagement Methodology

During proposal phase, task leaders from across the consortium flagged a significant number of areas where they would want or need input from the partner cities into their research tasks, either for providing the raw data or for the validation of results within their contexts. To reduce this becoming an overwhelming burden, either for the cities themselves or for the local stakeholders that would be connected to TIMBERHAUS, T5.1 planned to streamline these asks into specific moments planned over the course of the project where multiple topics would be tackled in one go, and for which our local partners could plan for.

To ensure a balance between inclusion, reaching a wide audience, and meaningful engagement locally, events were planned to consist of both in-person ones and online sessions. The initial suggested breakdown of this engagement is detailed in the table below.

Type of event	No. of events per city	Content (feedback for)	Format of the events
Physical stakeholder summits	3 2-day events	NEB in practice; Co-define scenarios; Co-develop decarbonisation strategies and development of SDM and Strategy Games	Physical events with invitation of all relevant local stakeholders with possible group- or stakeholder-specific sessions
Online workshops	6 workshops per city	Co-define large scale demonstration requirements; City action plans to fast track wood construction; Roadmaps to mainstream multi-storey wood buildings; Replication webinars	Online with targeted groups of stakeholders especially the communities of practice established
Travelling exhibitions	1 per city	Travelling roadshow of project solutions and results	Physical

Table 2: Engagement events summary

This division of events remains broadly accurate, with minor amendments being made and with the timing of the Stakeholder Summits themselves better refined and the topics split re-assessed. The most up to visual of the engagement framework is seen in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Engagement Framework

Broadly, the methodology integrates:

- **Central coordination**, ensuring alignment, consistency, access to knowledge, and integration across the cities;
- **Local communities of practice**, supporting place-based innovation and empowerment of local stakeholders;
- **Cross-sector dialogue**, focusing on the breadth of the stakeholder value chain from forest to city.

Engagement is then operationalised through a mix of:

- **Participatory formats**, such as through the workshops, strategy games, and summits;
- **Qualitative and quantitative research**, through interviews, surveys, and focus groups;
- Continuous **feedback loops** both with the cities and with the local stakeholders who form the communities of practice.

This is explained in the visuals in Figures 16 and 17 which have been used in the Stakeholder Summits with local stakeholders to describe a collaboration model that connects local ecosystems to transnational and EU-level knowledge exchange.

How we work together

Figure 16. Diagram visualising the Common Engagement Methodology

How we work together

Figure 17. Diagram visualising the Common Engagement Methodology between the cities

Overall, the TIMBERHAUS common engagement methodology balances the flexibility needed for such engagement with a clear structure to support local action and knowledge exchange. We will now look at how this approach has worked in practice.

4.3. Testing through Implementation

Whilst the methodology set out above remains the foundation of our approach and our reference document, the reality of meaningful place-based engagement often requires adaptation and flexibility to the local context.

One of the key elements that varied from proposal and theory to actual implementation was the idea that we would be able to deliver many of the engagement moments, particularly online sessions, collaboratively with all three cities. Whilst the intention behind this was a positive one, in particular to share learnings across the three cities, particularly in the first phase of the project, the pace at which each city progresses differed significantly.

Following the first collaborative stakeholder mapping session, detailed above in section 3.2, the relevant partners met to assess the results and discuss the approach. Based on the experience up until that point, it was agreed that moving forward engagement would be done with the cities separately as the first course of action, and that we would subsequently organise spaces for knowledge sharing between them, which to date have happened during the General Assemblies and the Stakeholder Summits in particular. The rationale for this approach was due to the divergence in language, local context, level of ambition, and experience with wood construction to date.

We will now look at the internal coordination effort, before taking a nuanced city by city look at how this engagement approach has ultimately manifested itself.

4.3.1. Internal Coordination

Noting that the CEM relates predominantly to the tasks carried out by task leaders from CKIC, URBA and ETHZ across WP5 and WP6, all of which require varying level of city engagement, bi-weekly coordination calls were held between the three partners for the first 12 months of the project. These meetings were used to align on our respective asks for the cities, to plan upcoming engagement moments, and to ensure that our communication to the cities came as one voice without duplication or confusion.

Steps were taken to support the tracking of this engagement and to capture the key points. Whilst the initial intention was to do so through the Airtable approach, as set out in section 3.3, this plan proved less effective than intended. Instead, partners utilised a central Teams message channel and a tracking document was set up for each city, where key points of each interaction should be captured.

The level to which said documents have been used differs depending on the city, noting that the cities themselves come with different approaches to coordination, as we will now explore in more detail.

4.3.2. Baia Mare

In the case of Baia Mare, thanks to the support of local partners, we have been able to progress with in person engagement and take significant steps in their progress within TIMBERHAUS to date. Whilst it was a slower start due to a reshuffling within the local administration, we ran a second kick-off exercise with the new team at Baia Mare in April 2025. This involved the project and assistant project manager, several technical experts, a communication colleague, and the stakeholder engagement lead.

Whilst this meeting made clear that Baia Mare could be considered less advanced in terms of building with wood from an environmental and ecological perspective, this project was recognised as an opportunity for them to progress, particularly reflecting on their rich history of woodwork, craftsmen and traditions. Since then, local outreach has been spearheaded by the local municipality who hold many of the current relations, both within Baia Mare and in the wider Maramureş region. This was evidenced through the engagement at the first Stakeholder Summit held there, where participation was enthusiastic and well organised.

Through these early meetings and efforts to connect to local stakeholders, the following points can be drawn:

- The topic of wood construction in Baia Mare is a nuanced one, since they have a long tradition of use of wood, including wooden gates rich in heritage, but are facing a newer ‘tradition’ of building heavily in concrete and steel.
- Residents themselves care about their traditions, which could be an interesting leverage point within the project.
- There is strong potential to work with local architects and craftsmen.

The subsequent impact that this has had on our engagement approach includes:

- Trusting our local partner, i.e. Baia Mare Municipality, to hold and maintain relationships, with support from the consortium partners.
- Prioritising in-person engagement as far as possible.
- Delivering said engagement in local language to increase the impact of our outreach and meet stakeholders where they feel more comfortable.

Moving forward, we will continue to use the in-person Stakeholder Summits as a key moment for engagement and will continue to provide to support Baia Mare Municipality in their outreach between these events to maintain momentum.

4.3.3. Berlin

The city of Berlin, working in close collaboration with Tegel Projekt, represents an ambitious case study within TIMBERHAUS and an opportunity to push our research further. The Schumacher Quartier, a model neighbourhood for urban timber construction which will consist of more than 5,000 apartments for more than 10,000 residents is closely connected to the project and is far from the only example of large-scale building with timber in the city.

Given this experience, there are also a significant number of stakeholders who are already involved in the topic and several established stakeholder networks, including one managed by Tegel themselves who have a dedicated stakeholder engagement lead. The key objective was therefore to complement and strengthen these networks and the ongoing discussions, rather than to create a separate space which might dilute the interest or cause frustration with those who have already been pushing for progress.

From our early discussions around this, we could establish the following key points:

- There would need to be a clear value proposition to encourage stakeholders to engage.
- The possibility to connect the local stakeholders and their inputs to policy and decision makers at EU level was recognised as a role that TIMBERHAUS should play.
- Clear communication, timelines, and engagement moments needed to be mapped out in advance of stakeholder outreach.

To support this, the following steps were taken for our engagement approach:

- The creation of a one-pager in German which summarised the project, its goals, and explicitly highlighted how stakeholders could engage and what they would get out of it.
- The set up of monthly coordination meetings with the teams from CKIC, URBA, ETHZ, DEMOS, Berlin and Tegel as a shared space to provide updates on the work within WP5, to clarify and discuss in detail any asks that have recently been shared with the cities, or to gain useful feedback from them on how stakeholder engagement is being received.

Lastly, we recognise that the key to successful engagement in the case of Berlin will depend on the project's ability to provide technical advice, policy recommendations, and advocacy to address the specific issues that Berlin is facing in progressing further with their wood construction journey. This will be a recurring element of our approach, and we will continue to assess how we can best contribute to this over the next phase.

4.3.4. Siena

Siena is a unique city within the climate-smart use of wood space, in that with a city centre that is rich in cultural heritage and where inner-city construction is highly protected and regulated, there is less of a strong ambition to build with wood within the city centre. On the other hand, beyond the walls of the city, Tuscany is one of Italy's most forested regions and Siena itself is diving into sustainable construction more broadly.

In addition to this, the team within the Commune of Siena changed early on in the project and were transparent about this being a project where they brought a different level of ambition and experience compared to that of Berlin, for example. To support the team, we held another kick-off in April 2025, similar to with Baia Mare, to meet the new team, establish their current understanding and baseline, and to discuss next steps. This meeting was attended by the project manager and representatives from the municipality, but also the University of Siena (working on the European Living Lab) and the associated Santa Chiara Fab Lab.

Through this meeting and early efforts to connect to the local stakeholders, the following points were drawn:

- The topic of wood construction itself is a relatively new one within Siena, and therefore the relevant level of ambition is also relatively low.
- The city themselves would need support in terms of reaching a wider audience in the forest to city value chain.
- The connection to the EU and further involvement in EU projects could be of particular interest.
- In-person engagement is preferred, with fewer online moments and flexibility to their timetable.

Based on this, the engagement approach for Siena has been tailored to incorporate:

- Engaging as far as possible in Italian as the local language to meet the local stakeholders where they are more comfortable.
- Broadening the approach to go beyond Siena and look to the wider Tuscany region, which could be particularly beneficial when considering the link between urban and rural in wood construction.
- Focusing on in-person engagement over online sessions. Specifically, we placed significant focus on the first in-person Stakeholder Summit (which will be fully detailed in the section below)
- Designating one Italian-speaking project member as the first port of call for Siena in the project.

Our experience with Siena, as with Baia Mare and Berlin, has highlighted the importance of strong local partnerships, of both empowering and trusting our cities to navigate local outreach, and of creating a framework in which flexibility is supported to address the nuances across each city in a way that best supports their respective goals.

5. Communities of Practice

5.1. Introduction

Closely connected to both the stakeholder mapping and analysis and the common engagement methodology is the subsequent establishment of communities of practice, for which TIMBERHAUS will establish or strengthen multi-actor communities of practice in partner cities (connecting them to the existing Build-in-Wood Community) for co-creation activities.

For the purpose of this document, communities of practices are described as a group of individuals and/or organisations who share an interest in a specific topic, in this case the climate-smart use of wood, and come together to contribute to the furthering of said topic. In the context of TIMBERHAUS, such a community of practice, particularly at the partner city level, is designed as an effective way of gaining traction, streamlining engagement moments, and gathering a range of experts from across the forest-to-city value chain to both contribute to the project and consequently to share the insights and results from TIMBERHAUS beyond the project to their networks.

This section will therefore detail the background assessment into the possibilities for existing or new communities of practice, the discussions held with partner cities around the best approach, and ultimately how these have manifested in practice in Baia Mare, Berlin and Siena respectively, most notably through what we refer to as Stakeholder Summits.

5.2. Background context and assessment

Before progressing with the creation of new and structured communities of practice, the consortium considered the current landscape and stakeholder appetite, looking into the traction that was received through stakeholder mapping, the existing networks in place, and the value proposition of establishing new ones.

In particular, discussions were held with each of the partner cities to understand their wishes and the current landscape of stakeholders within their reach. This was relevant since whilst the stakeholder mapping exercise detailed above produced a long list of local stakeholders from across the forest-to-city value chain, we relied on our contacts in each city to add the more human element to this spreadsheet. We sought to understand the existing interpersonal relationships between the cities and their stakeholders, what opportunities or tensions may already exist, and if or how these stakeholders already meet in other forums for similar purposes to those that TIMBERHAUS proposes.

Whilst the exact situation was different for each partner city, the conclusion that was reached collectively was that the most effective way to maintain engagement with local stakeholders was not through the formal establishment of a new community of practice

with additional governance structures and fixed membership, but rather through what we refer to as Stakeholder Summits.

These summits, already planned as a key element of our stakeholder outreach and engagement at partner city level under the CEM, would function as the local manifestation of communities of practice, with additional engagement carried out online between the summits. Three Stakeholder Summits are to be held in each partner city over the course of the project, complemented by the final travelling roadshow and the General Assemblies – the first ones of which prioritised our partner cities as the chosen host location to ensure the consortium had greater insight into the local context from early on.

The overarching rationale for this approach was grounded in the conclusion that more meaningful engagement could take place in-person with a larger group of interested stakeholders who would be attracted through these sessions to further contribute to online forums such as surveys, workshop and interviews. This was viewed as the most effective way of achieving the objectives of the task.

5.3. Existing networks & communities of practice

Whilst the decision was made to focus the communities of practice at local level through the Stakeholder Summits and through our local city partners, a number of existing networks were also considered during this phase. Of these, two in particular were deemed to be the most relevant, both of which we have either focused on integrating to date or are pinpointed as a feature of future engagement.

It should also be noted that in addition to the two networks detailed below, through the Collaboration Taskforce under T8.4 further connections are explored and activated, such as with the NEB Academy and the WoodStock project, funded under the same call as TIMBERHAUS.

5.3.1. Built by Nature Country Networks

One of the most relevant networks for the purpose of stakeholder engagement in specifically two of our three partner cities would be the Built by Nature country networks of both Germany and Italy, noting that this has the potential to support engagement in Berlin and Siena respectively. These networks are already established, with active members, and could therefore strengthen the engagement at local level through connecting TIMBERHAUS with already active individuals.

To date, connections have been established with the network leads of each to understand where we can best collaborate, as well as their key interests and research already carried out. In the case of Berlin, the recent Stakeholder Summit was attended by the Germany network lead, who also supported in the dissemination of a survey under D6.3 to collect perceptions on local historical and cultural traditions, craft and design languages in urban and rural areas, and wood use.

It should be noted that the networks have a slightly different focus than TIMBERHAUS since they focus exclusively on the demand side with a mission to transform the built

environment by promoting the responsible use of timber and biobased materials. In comparison, TIMBERHAUS looks across the value chain from supply through to demand. However, the overlap remains significant and we expect to continue this collaboration as the project progresses.

5.3.2. Build-in-Wood Community

Established under the Build-in-Wood project, the existing Build-in-Wood Community has been highlighted as a key connector with TIMBERHAUS. Consisting of over 2,300 members enthusiastic about wood construction and with a number of project partners overlapping between the two projects, this was a natural match.

Made up of multiple thematic and geographic sub-groups and advertising upcoming events, the Community has to date been used to increase our outreach for specific events, i.e. the Berlin Stakeholder Summit was advertised on the Germany channel and a number of members of that group were directly invited to attend where we felt this would be relevant.

The next steps will include a more strategic approach to the connection between the TIMBERHAUS communities of practice and the Build-in-Wood Community, in alignment with the expansion of the Build-in-Wood Design Guide under T3.3. A number of options will be set out and discussed between the relevant project partners, namely ICONS, URBA, DTI, WTA and CKIC, before progressing with more formal alignment.

5.4. Stakeholder Summits

Noting that a full report on the Stakeholder Summits will be produced in future under D6.5 once two summits have been held in each of the partner cities, for the purpose of this document, we will look at how the first ones have played out in each city, and how this connects to the wider engagement piece and the relevant next steps for each one to maintain engagement between now and the next summit in each location.

The general structure of each summit broadly aligned in terms of content and agenda, with some nuances depending on the needs and preferences of the city. Having said this, the key building blocks of the summits that we played around with were:

- An introduction to TIMBERHAUS
- An introduction to the New European Bauhaus initiative
- An introduction to the local context for forestry and wood use in construction, including expert speakers where relevant
- An interactive workshop to dive into the local and regional challenges and opportunities for the climate-smart use of wood, including priorities for future development
- Site visits, such as to a local school constructed from wood or a traditional woodworking session
- An interactive session focused around a strategy game created by ETHZ

Prior to each summit, we worked closely with the local partner to establish which of these elements fit best into their context, to refine the agenda, the stakeholder list, and to support in the development of content for outreach, such as posters, LinkedIn posts, and direct outreach.

The below canvases provide examples of the tools used during the interactive workshop for example, which transition from initially reviewing the challenges and opportunities, through to a deeper dive into understanding the root cause of selected challenges, and subsequently working on action statement to guide the pathways for future interventions.

Figure 18. The opportunities and challenges canvas from the Siena workshop

Figure 19. The problem tree from the Siena workshop

FROM CHALLENGE TO ACTION!
-DALLA SFIDA ALL'AZIONE!-

KEY CHALLENGE SFIDA PRINCIPALE	ACTION STATEMENT AZIONE PROPOSTA	VOTES VOTI

SUGGESTED STRUCTURE OF THE ACTION STATEMENT:
 IN THE WOOD VALUE CHAIN IN SIENA, THERE IS A NEED TO / LACK OF / OPPORTUNITY TO _____ WHICH IS WHY WE SUGGEST DEVELOPING / STRENGTHENING / IMPLEMENTING _____ IN ORDER TO ACHIEVE / CONTRIBUTE TO _____

STRUTTURA SUGGERITA PER LA FORMULAZIONE DELL'AZIONE:
 NELLA CATENA DEL VALORE DEL LEGNO DI SIENA ESISTE UN BISOGNO DI / UNA MANCANZA DI / UN'OPPORTUNITÀ DI _____ MOTIVO PER CUI SUGGERIAMO LO SVILUPPO / IL CONSOLIDAMENTO / L'IMPLEMENTAZIONE DI _____ PER RAGGIUNGERE / CONTRIBUIRE A _____

Figure 20. Canvas moving from Challenge to Action using vision statements in the Siena workshop

5.4.1. Baia Mare

The first Stakeholder Summit of the project was held in Baia Mare on 22nd and 23rd September 2025, directly after the city's 30th Chestnut Festival, and held at the Millennium Business Center and the ZBOR Youth Center.

The rationale for aligning with the Chestnut Festival was that by combining the two events, each would elevate the other and each could tap into the stakeholders invited to the other to increase outreach to those who may otherwise not have been involved. Working closely with the Baia Mare municipality, the summit was designed as a first effort at community building, activating the local community around TIMBERHAUS for future engagement, and to strengthen the public-private collaboration among local stakeholders.

Stakeholders represented included those from public administrations, forest management, culture and heritage, the construction and processing industry, and environmental services and waste management, as well as TIMBERHAUS project partners.

Figure 21. Visit to the Baia Mare Village Museum during the Stakeholder Summit in Baia Mare, September 2025

The agenda combined all the key elements of the summit, including a wood working demonstration, presentations from both TIMBERHAUS and local partners, an interactive workshop, a village museum visit, strategy game demonstration, a visit to a local producer and a tree planting.

Of particular interest for TIMBERHAUS was the workshop on the challenges and opportunities across the wood value chain in the city and wider region, an exercise that would be replicated with slight amendments across the three cities.

Figure 22. Workshop on the challenges and opportunities across the wood value chain during the Stakeholder Summit in Baia Mare, September 2025

Key takeaways from this workshop noted the following as the key challenges faced by the region: illegal forest exploitation, high cost of timber buildings, lack of qualified workforce, difficult maintenance of timber buildings, low awareness, timber not trendy/commonly used, low market demand.

From this workshop, two actions in particular were highlighted as actions to explore, namely:

- Tackling the issue of **illegal logging**, possibly through tech-based monitoring systems, adapting legislation and stricter enforcement, early education and awareness, and more rangers included in forest staff.
- Addressing the **high costs of wood buildings** and their raw materials, such as through the use of lower-grade wood, introducing financial incentives, efficient forest management, tree planting, traceability, improved processing tech; the involvement of banks, insurance companies, and government through incentives & property related taxes.

The strategy game exercise also generated significant interest amongst participants, demonstrating the value in focusing on more interactive approaches and moving away from traditional presenting formats. This will be further utilised in future summits in Baia Mare now that the strategy game created under T6.4 has progressed into a more detailed and locally grounded one.

As noted in section 4.3.2, our engagement with Baia Mare is significantly improved thanks to local connectors who navigate the communication between project partners and local

stakeholders. Following the stakeholder summit, a number of questions and follow-up interest was received in this way, which has been picked up directly.

The next Stakeholder Summit will be a moment to progress with concrete actions based on the previous challenges highlighted in the first summit. Between now and then, we will also focus on bridging the current gap between the personal networks and our recorded information with the project to support long term impact.

5.4.2. Siena

The first Stakeholder Summit in Siena was held on 27th & 28th November 2025, directly following the internal General Assembly and hosted in the Complesso Museale Santa Maria della Scala and the Palazzo Patrizi.

This was a particularly important moment since it was recognised that for Siena, the theme of climate-smart wood construction was a new topic for many of their local stakeholders, and as such the groundwork needed to be laid before more input could be provided to requests that had previously come in online.

The summit was designed as a key moment to activate the local community to generate interest in TIMBERHAUS longer term. The agenda therefore included an introduction to the topic, to the project and to what we mean by climate-smart use of wood in the first place, before moving onto the interactive activities, specifically a version of the workshop detailed previously on the challenges and opportunities for wood construction in Siena and the wider region.

The stakeholders represented included those from forest management, research and innovation, and environment and climate, but the largest groups represented were from architecture and public administration. Specifically, local stakeholders were represented through Ordine degli Architetti di Siena, Provincia di Siena, Università di Siena, FAB LAB UNISI, Consorzio Forestale, Associazione Le Mura, Collegio dei Periti Agrari di Siena, Imperiale Contrada della Giraffa, CONFINDUSTRIA Wood Sector, and the LAMAMBIENTE Company.

Thanks to the summit, progress was made in diving into the nuances of Siena's relationship with wood construction and how TIMBERHAUS can support this. From the workshop, the main challenges identified included:

- Limited production capacity and lack of specialised timber companies
- An absence of a strong tradition of wood construction, reinforced by cultural preferences for conventional materials
- Limited availability of structural timber and technical know-how, affecting local implementation

Whereas opportunities included:

- Strong cultural and construction heritage, offering a solid foundation for innovation

- Existing artisanal skills and local entrepreneurship, with potential to adapt to modern timber construction
- A growing interest in sustainability and circular economy approaches, creating momentum for change

Moving forward, TIMBERHAUS will support local actors in their priority actions, specifically through looking at policy, awareness-raising, and the promotion of wood-based construction and renovation through integration into local strategies.

In addition to the content learnt, an organisational and logistic one was also confirmed from Baia Mare during this summit, namely the value of interactive exercises. From the overall agenda, the workshop and the strategy game (pictured in Figures 20 and 21) proved by far the most popular elements of the agenda with participants.

Figure 23. Workshop on the challenges and opportunities across the wood value chain during the Stakeholder Summit in Siena, November 2025

Figure 24. Strategy Game at the Stakeholder Summit in Siena, November 2025

Looking forward to the next steps for the local stakeholders, during the event, participants were encouraged to express their interest for future engagement in the project through a survey where they could indicate which elements of the project would be of most benefit or interest to them. In addition to this, Siena is recently strengthening the involvement of the Siena FabLab to further support their outreach and to connect the topic to a wider audience.

5.4.3. Berlin

The final Stakeholder Summit that was held for the first round in the cities was in Berlin on 17th and 18th March 2026, hosted at the Infocenter Berlin TXL. It gathered stakeholders from across the value chain industries, with the largest representation coming from public administrations, academia and research, and professional organisations and networks connected to wood construction.

As detailed in section 4.3.3, the topic of wood construction is not a new one to Berlin, and as such the agenda was structured in an effort to ensure that we were adding to the topic rather than going back to basics. For this reason, our partners in Berlin organised for well-respected speakers (e.g. the President of the Berlin Chamber of Architects) in their industries to present to participants as a selling point of the summit. The agenda included

a brief introduction to TIMBERHAUS itself, highlighting where this connected to ongoing initiatives within the Berlin region, before progressing with expert presentations.

During the preparation for the summit, the workshop structure was slightly refined to recognise that there was already some information on the challenges and opportunities in this region. We therefore predetermined thematic groups that participants could select from to encourage deeper discussion on a specific element of value chain. The four thematic groups, informed through discussions with Berlin & Tegel were:

- Material & Construction
- Market & Logistics
- Education & Research
- Policies & Regulations

Interestingly, when the groups divided it became evident that the market and logistics topic was the least selected, a lesson that is noted for future sessions in terms of broadening the stakeholder representatives present.

A priority from this session was to gain further detail on the key challenges and opportunities already identified within Berlin, enabling TIMBERHAUS to become a helpful partner to local stakeholders in further exploring the action points identified. Through the workshop, we were able to confirm some of the assumptions around challenges and opportunities, with the former identified as the following:

- Limited production capacity and fragmented value chain
- Complex regulatory and permitting procedures
- Insufficient funding and financial barriers
- Weak links between education, research, and practical application in industry
- Gaps in procurement processes and their implementation

As noted, the success of TIMBERHAUS in Berlin will depend on our ability to support them in addressing these challenges. Noting that the priority actions were those highlighted below, this is where some of our efforts will be focusing as a next step to ensure clear progress by the next summit.

- Strengthening education, training, and knowledge exchange between academia and practice
- Improving and simplifying regulatory and permitting processes
- Developing funding schemes and financial incentives to support timber construction
- Supporting local production capacity and strengthening value chains
- Promoting timber construction through public projects and awareness-raising

Following the summit, a summary document was created to be shared with local partners, along with a link for participants to sign up for further engagement moments, with the next summit there pencilled in for January 2027.

Marking the final summit of the first round, the foundations are now laid for subsequent sessions both online and in-person. Collectively, these summits, followed by the travelling roadshow to present the project's results combine into a methodology to translate local perspectives into tangible actions at local, regional, national, and EU level.

5.5. Next steps for the community of practice

As detailed, stakeholder engagement is an iterative process and as such we are consistently assessing its efficacy both with the organising partners, our partner cities and local stakeholders. Informal feedback was sought and discussed with the organising team directly after each city held its first summit, and following the conclusion of all three, a streamlined feedback form was provided to each of the cities to run through this in more detail with some distance from it which could allow for greater objectivity. From this feedback, a number of lessons learnt can be established which we are actively taking into the next round of organising summits and continuous engagement. This includes but is not limited to the following:

- Focusing on **interactive moments** rather than presentational formats is both more appealing for the audience to attend and is where the most valuable insights can come from. This was particularly evident with the popularity of the strategy game during both the Baia Mare and Siena Stakeholder Summits for example and as such a bigger focus is placed on the interactive elements moving forward.
- Careful consideration and planning of the **language** that the summit is held in prior to the event. In the cases of both Siena and Baia Mare, the summits were planned to be in English and were discussed as so, but the reality in person was that for many of the participants, carrying it out in the local language was the preferred option. The approach differed, i.e. in Baia Mare one of the local partners carried out live translation, whereas in Siena project partners who spoke Italian stepped in to facilitate the sessions. Moving forward, we will ensure clarity in advance of the events both for the participants and the project partners of the language choices made.
- Considering **breaking up the two-day summit** into specific sections that stakeholders can join which are meaningful on their own, but which collectively make up one summit when pieced together. This would allow us to dive deeper into topics with the most relevant individuals for said topic, whilst also asking for a smaller time commitment from them which is easier to manage.
- **Improved outreach** to the stakeholder groups that to date have been less well represented than others in these summits, for example forest managers, and those on the construction side have been harder to reach than those in architecture, the public sector and in research. We will reconsider the topics, format, and outreach approach to target these groups more effectively.

Factoring in the above lessons, moving forward and bearing in mind that this is an exercise of iteration, we are exploring slight changes to the format of the summits to make them more meaningful for our local partners.

6. Conclusion

6.1. Onwards Implementation

Fundamentally, the work detailed above can be defined as having laid the groundwork for the ongoing implementation of stakeholder mapping, analysis, and community engagement across the rest of the project, and ideally to be continued post project. With T5.1 formally concluding at M18, the three components of the task are continued in other tasks and delivered through WP5, 6 and 7 as a collective, the details of which are summarised below.

As noted throughout this deliverable, this remains an iterative piece of work, ensuring that we are consistently assessing our engagement approach and being agile to feedback on what is or is not working at a local level. This will remain the core of our approach moving forward.

6.2. Stakeholder Mapping

As part of ongoing implementation, Task 6.2 has assumed ownership of the stakeholder mapping process, continuing to work with cities and WP6 partners to populate and develop the four Excel spreadsheets. Task 6.2 will use the spreadsheets as the structured foundation for its System Dynamics Models of the wood construction value chain.

As the sheets are developed and refined, they will also support more targeted outreach for the second and third Stakeholder Summits, ensuring that the mapping work delivers increasing value across the remaining life of the project.

6.3. Common Engagement Methodology

The experience of developing and applying the Common Engagement Methodology within TIMBERHAUS highlights both the value and the complexity of structuring meaningful, place-based engagement across diverse contexts in a project such as this.

While the initial framework provided a necessary foundation for alignment, the key to its success has been in its adaptability. The variations across the cities demonstrate the need for a balance between principles and flexibility, on the one hand allowing for comparison, learnings, and knowledge exchange between the cities, while on the other hand allowing for the engagement to be shaped by local stakeholders and their specific expectations and needs.

Looking ahead, the CEM will continue to evolve, for example, we may re-assess which topics are covered under the Stakeholder Summits and which are addressed through focus groups or online workshops instead. We will further focus on maintaining and

deepening our relationships with local stakeholders and improving the feedback loops between the cities themselves.

This work sits across tasks within WP5 and 6 led by CKIC, URBA and ETHZ, and as such the partners will closely collaborate to ensure we remain aligned.

6.4. Communities of Practice

Whilst the first round of Stakeholder Summits is completed, there is a significant amount of work to be continued to build upon them and ensure that we maintain momentum for local stakeholders. The focus moving forwards is therefore on:

- Incorporating, as far as possible, the key focus areas of the cities into our research work in WP5, e.g. where the Berlin workshop highlighted improving and simplifying regulatory and permitting processes as a key action, this would be a good area to include for finding best practice under T5.4.
- Planning for the next round of Stakeholder Summits, noting that we expect the Baia Mare and Siena ones to be held between October and November 2026, and Berlin's in early 2027. Whilst this is formally housed under T6.3, it relies on significant contributions from across WP5 and 6, such as T6.1 (NEB approach implementation) and T6.4 (strategy games). This activity also includes a reconsideration of the approach to the summits, as detailed in section 5.5, possibly incorporating different smaller workshops and focus groups that collectively make up one larger event.
- The refinement and subsequent testing of the strategy games developed under T6.4. Considered a particularly effective way of bringing stakeholders with differing views together, this will be crucial to the next phases of the TIMBERHAUS local engagement.

To be effective in this approach, we rely on close collaboration with our respective city partners who in most cases hold the relationships with the local stakeholders. As such, we are also exploring how TIMBERHAUS can better support our cities in cultivating these relationships and their involvement in our communities of practice.

At this stage in the project, the groundwork has been laid, and through the deployment of tasks across WP5, 6 and 7 will continue to be strengthened, ensuring that TIMBERHAUS research and technical and policy developments are designed for the audience who will ultimately take them forward at local, national and EU level.

Annex 1

Invitations for the first round of stakeholder summits.

1st TIMBERHAUS Summit in Baia Mare:

The Past, Present and Future of Wood in Baia Mare

What is it about:

Taking place in the days following Baia Mare's 30th Chestnut Festival, the **first TIMBERHAUS Summit (22-23 of September 2023)** invites local and regional actors to explore the **climate-smart use of wood in the construction sector.**

1st TIMBERHAUS Summit in Baia Mare will bring together project partners, local and regional public authorities, private sector representatives, professional and cultural associations, educational and research institutions, and NGOs for a two-day programme of **presentations, site visits and interactive sessions.**

Together, we aim to spark collaboration and ideas around the climate-smart use of wood — exploring its historical significance in Maramureş and Baia Mare, the current political and development landscape, and the challenges and opportunities for advancing climate-smart forestry and construction practices in the city and region.

PHOTOS BY: CJ Maramureş

Dates:

22-23 September 2025

Location:

- Millennium Business Center M1, Vulturul Negru Hall, 2 Vasile Lucaciu Street, Baia Mare
- ZBOR Youth Center

Main Organiser:

Baia Mare Municipality

Co-organisers:

Urbasofia, Climate-KIC,
ETH Zurich

1st TIMBERHAUS Summit in Siena: Linking Heritage and Carbon Neutrality for Sustainable Futures

Taking place on 27-28 November 2025, the TIMBERHAUS Summit in Siena invites local and regional actors to explore the climate-smart use of wood in the construction sector.

What it is about:

The summit will bring together project partners, local and regional public authorities, private sector representatives, professional and cultural associations, educational and research institutions, and NGOs for a 2-day programme of presentations, site visits and interactive sessions.

Together, we will spark collaboration and explore the interplay between heritage and the push for carbon neutrality for sustainable futures. We will dive into the local context in Siena, the city's commitment to climate action and the role of wood within this, and the challenges and opportunities for advancing climate-smart forestry and construction practices in the city and region.

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Dates:

27 - 28 November 2025

Location:

- Complesso Museale Santa Maria della Scala (Day 1)
- Palazzo Patrizi, Via di Città, 75 (Day 2)

Main Organiser:

Siena Municipality

Co-organisers:

Climate-KIC
ETH Zurich
Urbasofia

Co-funded by
the European Union

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Ministero dell'Università e
Ricerca
Commissione europea
Fondo di Sviluppo
Regionale

Finanziamento a favore della
Ricerca e dell'Innovazione
Dati e servizi per il sistema
regionale di ricerca e
innovazione

TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Meeting in Berlin:

Birth and Rebirth of Wooden Buildings.

The TIMBERHAUS Stakeholder Meeting in Berlin invites local and regional actors to **explore the advantages and disadvantages of building and renovating with wood** in the current Berlin urban context.

What it is about:

Hosted at Berlin TXL, the event will bring together local and regional public authorities, project partners, private sector representatives, architecture, educational and research institutions, and those seeking to **further the climate-smart use of wood in the construction in Berlin.**

We are looking forward to a programme of expert **presentations** and interactive **workshops**. Together, we will share insights, spark collaboration, and dive deeper into the **challenges, opportunities,** and pathways for building in wood in Berlin.

Photo by Thomas Mayer

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Dates:

17 - 18 March 2026

Location:

Infocenter Berlin TXL - Tegel Projekt GmbH, Urban Tech Republic, Gebäude V, Flughafen Tegel 1, 13405 Berlin

Main Organiser:

Berlin Senate Department for Urban Development, Building and Housing & Tegel Projekt GmbH.

Co-organisers:

CKIC, URBA, ETHZ

Co-funded by
the European Union

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Österreichische Zimmerei
Konföderation
Confédération Suisse
Confederazione Italiana
Zimmerei

Federal Department of Economic Affairs
Industrie und Handel
Hans-Sachsler für Holz, Holzwerkstoffe und Holz